

Effect of Pressure on superconducting properties of endohedral gallide cluster based superconductor $\text{Mo}_8\text{Ga}_{41}$

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Endohedral gallide cluster is found to be a structural motif that favors existence of superconductivity. Some of the examples are $\text{Mo}_8\text{Ga}_{41}$, $\text{Mo}_6\text{Ga}_{31}$, ReGa_5 , PuCoGa_5 [1-3]. We synthesized $\text{Mo}_8\text{Ga}_{41}$ superconductor that shows superconducting transition at 9.8 K. The upper critical field (H_{c2}), lower critical field (H_{c1}), coherence length (ξ) and penetration depth (λ) are found to be 11.8T, 150G, 5.2nm and 148nm respectively. On applying pressure (0-1.1GPa) the transition temperature decreases from 9.8 to 9.6 K while almost two fold enhancement in critical current density (J_c) is evaluated from M-H loop taken at 2K ($\sim 10^5 \text{ A-cm}^{-2}$). Similar enhancement in J_c was also estimated from M-H loop taken at 7K and 9K. The Kramer's fitting for normalized pinning force F_p vs. reduced field ($h=H/H^*$), where H^* is irreducible field yields the presence of multiple pinning mechanism based on point, surface and volume pinning. The double exponential model fitting on J_c vs. reduced field h indicates two gap superconductivity[4].

Keywords: Superconductivity, Pinning, Critical current density, Pinning force density.

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